

EXAMINATION OF THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND TEAM WORKABILITY OF SPORTS STUDENTS ACCORDING TO A RANGE OF VARIABLES

Orcan Mızrak¹, Ali Gürbüz², Emre Belli¹, M.A. Kurudirek³,

Yeşim Songün Bayraktaroğlu⁴

¹ Faculty of Sports Science, Atatürk University, ERZURUM/TURKEY

² Rectorate-Physical Education and Sports, Mimar Sinan Fine Arts University, ISTANBUL/TURKEY

³ School of Physical Education and Sports, Kafkas University, KARS/TURKEY

⁴ School of Physical Education and Sports, Gümüşhane University, GÜMÜŞHANE/TURKEY

Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the communication skills and team workability of students educated in sports education in universities according to a range of variables.

In the study, a personal information form was used to identify the university, department, class and sports branches of participants. The communication skills scale developed by Ersanlı and Balcı in 1998 was used to determine communication skills. For the determination of team workability, the Team Workability Scale developed by Tuncer in 2008 was used. 165 Students from Atatürk and Kafkas University participated in the study. Frequency analysis and parametric statistical analyses were used in the study. As a result of the study, it was determined that the participants had moderate levels ($X=3,56\pm,861$) of communication skills and the majority of the participants have responsibility ($n=105$ %64).

According to the variables of the communication skills and team workability of the students who studied sports education in universities, the communication skills levels did not change statistically according to the universities and departments variables of the participants. The highest average of communication skills amongst the participants are mental skills. ($X=3,86\pm,414$). The lowest average of the communication skills of the participants are behavioral. ($X=2,44\pm,616$). On the other hand, it has been determined that the team sports athletes among the participants have high averages on Collaboration and Teamwork in team workability. ($n=98$ %59,39).

Key words: communication skills, team workability, sports students

Introduction

Communication skills

Individuals are constantly redefined within their relationships. It is unthinkable to consider a person that does not have any relationship with other people. The nature of a person's relationships determines the quality of that person's life. Self-awareness and a relationship with other people and nature brings about a meaningful life (Cüceloğlu, D 2004). Furthermore, maintaining this meaningful relationship is only possible with communication.

The term communication is derived from the Latin word "communis", which means "common". Due to its etymology, the word "communication" refers to partnership, socialization and coexistence. Individuals communicate the rules, values and beliefs in society through communication (Tevrüz, S 1997).

Communication skills are "effective response and effective listening skills, which enable encoding and transmission of messages sent and interpreting the messages received correctly" (Deniz, 2003:8). Communication skills can be summarized as sensitivity to verbal and non-verbal messages, effective listening and

effective response (Korkut, 2004). Cüceloğlu defines communication in the following way: "It is the exchange of emotion and thought between people in general" (cf. Çetinkaya Ö, Alpaslan M A 2011).

Communication skills in communication activity are very important in acquiring sensitivity, especially in understanding others and perceiving their feelings and thoughts by identifying with them. The most important factor in achieving behavioral change is communication skills. Granvold (1994) addresses communication skills within the social skills and states that these skills support successful interpersonal relationships. He considers four cognitive and behavioral skills required for interpersonal relationships and social support.

The skills that enable a healthier communication can be summarized as effective listening and effective response. These skills can be listed in detail as asking appropriate questions, summarizing, repeating with other words, reacting with keywords, identifying and appropriately reflecting other people's behavior, words and emotions, testing their understanding, and giving effective feedback (Coursen, D and Thomas, J 1989).

Although some believe that communication skills are innate and intuitive, many studies show that most of the communication techniques have a characteristic learnable and teachable (Buckman, 2001, Egan, 1994 cf. Korkut Owen and Bugay 2014). Opinions about the kinds of skills involved in communication skills can vary. According to one opinion, communication skills deal with verbal, vocal-based, physical, tactile, gesture-based messages and various mixtures of these messages.

Team workability

Team workability can be seen as a topic that was first discussed indirectly in the late 19th century. People's relationship with their colleagues, managers and other people in their working environments has been the subject of many studies. The industrial establishments, which gained momentum after the industrial revolution, paved the way for more people to do various work in groups. This has further increased the units in a workplace and the importance of

coordination between those working in those units. Since the most valuable and powerful source of business is human resources, it is vital for people to be in harmony with each other in terms of productivity.

Schein's group concept is a structure consisting of more than two individuals associated with each other, which call themselves a group and embraces each other psychologically. From this point of view, the difference between the concept of group and "people who came together by chance" is the communication, awareness and the acceptance of the group as an entity.

Unlike groups, Adair defines teams as "communities with absolute goals and common interests". Another definition states that a team is a community formed by two or more individuals who are interdependent and act together to reach predetermined goals. A team emerging as a result of this common goal must serve the interests of the individuals that form the team in question. On the other hand, the individuals who form the team must also serve the interests of the team as well as their own personal interests. This uncovers a kind of synergy called team spirit. Thanks to this cooperation, teammates can work as a team and achieve the desired goals even if they are not physically close. For businesses, individuals who have a team spirit as well as a commitment to their team and organization are more valuable than independent, isolated individuals who act alone. Organizations idealize the individuals who are open, able to express themselves, able to find solutions to problems, and can work as a team, and these qualities are considered to be future employment skills.

An organizational culture based on teamwork, trust in employees, providing authority as well as providing feedback on various matters brings about a positive effect on their motivations. In this context, it is necessary to ensure that employees develop an "organizational identification" and "organizational adoption" by giving priority to teamwork. Their fears must be eliminated by improving mutual trust, understanding and production among employees.

What makes teams valuable is their ability to do a task that requires more than can be achieved on an individual basis, in a more successful manner with fewer people.

Method

The aim of this study is to examine the communication skills and team workability of students who are educated in sports education in universities according to a range of variables. In the study, a personal information form was used to identify the university, department, class and sports branches of participants. The

communication skills scale developed by Ersanlı and Balcı in 1998 was used to determine communication skills. For the determination of team workability, the Team Workability Scale developed by Tuncer in 2008 was used. 165 Students from Atatürk (n=77) and Kafkas University (n=88) participated in the study. Frequency analysis and parametric statistical analyzes (an independent samples T test and one way ANOVA) were used in the study.

Findings

Table 1. Information Related to Participants' Demographic Characteristics.

Gender	N	%
Male	104	63,1
Female	61	36,9
University	N	%
Atatürk University	77	46,7
Kafkas University	88	53,3
Department	N	%
Department of Physical Education and Sport Teaching	42	25,5
Department of Training Education	43	26,1
Department of Sports Management	80	48,5
Class	N	%
1	36	21,8
2	40	24,2
3	45	27,3
4	44	26,7
Sports Branch	N	%
Individual Sports	67	40,6
Team Sports	98	59,4
Total	165	100

It is revealed that when considering the distributions related to gender of participants, 36.9% of them are women with 61 people, 63.1% of them are men with 165 people; when considering the distributions related to university 49.7% of them are from Atatürk University with 77 people, 53.3% of them are from Kafkas University with 88 people; when considering the distributions related to departments, 25.5% of them come from the department of physical education and sports teaching with 42 people, 26.1% of them are from the department of education training with 43 people, 48.5% of them

are students of the department of sports management with 80 people; when considering the distributions related to class 21.8% of them are first year students with 36 people, 24.2% of them are second year students with 40 people, 27.3% of them are third year students with 45 people and 26.2% of them are fourth year students with 44 people; when considering the distributions related to their branch of sports 40.6% of them re individual sports athletes with 67 people, 59.4% of them are team sports players with 98 people.

Table 2. Communication Skills and Team Workability Comparison of Participants according to Gender. (T-Test)

Com. Skills	Gender	N	X	s.d	t	p
	Com. Skills	Male	104	3,68	,398	-3,098
Female		61	3,48	,430		
Team Work	Male	104	3,39	,380	1,648	,158
	Female	61	3,25	,421		

(p<0,05)

When the obtained data is analyzed, as a result of communications skills and team workability, a significant difference hasn't been found in terms of comparison of participants according to gender,. (p<0,05) According to this, male students (X=3,68±,398) have higher communication skill levels than the female

students (X =3.48±,430). In terms of team workability comparison of participants according to gender, a significant difference hasn't been found. (p<0,05) According to this, male students (X=3,39±,380) have higher team workability levels than the female students (X =3.25±,421).

Table 3. Communication Skills and Team Workability Comparison of Participants according to Universities. (T-Test)

Com. Skills	Universities	N	X	s.d	t	p
	Com. Skills	Atatürk University	88	3,5	,401	-2,958
Kafkas University		77	3,35	,239		
Team Work	Atatürk University	88	3,44	,440	-3,027	,214
	Kafkas University	77	3,35	,354		

(p<0,05)

When the obtained data is analyzed, as a result of communications skills and team workability comparison of participants according to universities, a significant difference hasn't been found. (p<0,05) According to this, Atatürk University students (X=3,5±,401) have higher communication skill levels than the Kafkas University students (X =3.35±,239).

According to team workability comparison of participants universities, a significant difference hasn't been found. (p<0,05) According to this, Atatürk University students (X=3,35±,354) have team workability levels higher than the Kafkas University students (X =3.44±,440).

Table 4. Communication Skills and Team Workability Comparison of Participants according to Sports Branches. (T-Test)

Com. Skills	Sports Branches	N	X	s.d	t	p
	Com. Skills	Individual Sports	67	3,39	,363	-1,117
Team Sports		98	3,45	,327		
Team Work	Individual Sports	67	3,41	,774	-1,459	,587
	Team Sports	98	3,55	,438		

(p<0,05)

When obtained data of communications skills and team workability is analyzed in terms of comparison of participants according to sports branches, a significant difference hasn't been found. ($p < 0,05$) According to this, team sports players ($X = 3,45 \pm ,327$) have communication skill levels higher than the individual sports athletes

($X = 3,39 \pm ,363$). In comparison of participants according to sports branches, a significant difference hasn't been found. ($p < 0,05$) According to this, team sports players ($X = 3,55 \pm ,438$) have team workability levels which are higher than the individual sports athletes ($X = 3,41 \pm ,774$).

Table 5. Communication Skills and Team Workability Comparison of Participants According to Departments. (One Way ANOVA)

		Departments	N	X	s.d	F	p
Com. Skills		Department of Physical Education and Sport Teaching	43	3,47	,216	2,297	,104
		Department of Training Education	42	3,33	,267		
		Department of Sports Management	80	3,46	,418		
Team Work		Department of Physical Education and Sport Teaching	43	3,39	,664	,536	,586
		Department of Training Education	42	3,29	,472		
		Department of Sports Management	80	3,32	,585		

($p < 0,05$)

When the obtained data is analyzed according to educational departments, no significant difference has been found in terms of communication skills and team workability comparison of participants. ($p < 0,05$) According to this, department of physical education and sport teaching students ($X = 3,47 \pm ,216$) have higher communication skill levels than the other

departments' students. A significant difference hasn't been found in team workability comparison of participants according to educational departments. ($p < 0,05$) According to this, department of physical education and sport teaching students ($X = 3,39 \pm ,664$) have higher team workability levels than the other departments' students.

Table 6. Communication Skills and Team Workability Comparison of Participants According to Classes. (One Way ANOVA)

		Classes	N	X	s.d	F	p
Com. Skills		1	36	3,39	,411	,720	,541
		2	40	3,48	,234		
		3	45	3,39	,431		
		4	44	3,45	,254		
Team Work		1	36	3,36	,423	3,568	,815
		2	40	3,57	,420		
		3	45	3,38	,425		
		4	44	3,29	,305		

No significant difference has been found in terms of communication skills and team workability when obtained data is analyzed in comparison of participants according to classes. ($p < 0,05$) According to this, year 2 students ($X=3,48\pm,234$) have higher communication skill levels than students of other class. In

comparison of participants according to classes, a significant difference in team workability hasn't been found. ($p<0,05$) According to this, class 2 students ($X=3,57\pm,420$) have higher team workability levels than the other classes' students.

Table 7. Communication Skills and Team Workability Correlation Levels (Pearson Correlation)

Communication Skills	Pearson Correlation	Communication Skills	Team Workability
	P	1	.492**
N	165	.000	165
Team Workability	Pearson Correlation	.492**	1
	P	.000	
N	165	165	

($p<0,01$)

According to the correlation analysis results, it was determined that there was a positive correlation between the communication skills and adaptation to teamwork ($r=.492, p<0,01$).

Discussion and Conclusion

As a result of this study, which investigates the communication skills and teamwork compatibility of undergraduate students receiving sport education according to various demographic variables, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of communication skills and adaptation to teamwork.

Considering the communication skills and adaptation to teamwork according to the genders of the participants, male participants were found to have higher averages than female participants. It has also been observed in other studies that effective communication skills may change depending on gender (Korkut, 1996, Moskal, 1997, Korkut, 2005, Gölönü and Karıcı, 2010). Communication skills follow a different course of development beginning from childhood. For example, female children prefer playing alone in their early childhood, whereas male children prefer playing in groups at the same period. This may explain why males have a higher level of communication skills and a

higher level of adaptation to teamwork than females.

Looking at communication skills and adaptation to teamwork according to the universities of the participants, students at the Atatürk University were found to have higher averages than the students studying at Kafkas University. Atatürk University is larger than Kafkas University in terms of its number of students. The number of students is also to the advantage of Atatürk University in terms of the sports education provided. An environment with more people can bring about more communication. Thus, this may explain the higher communication skills score averages of the students at Atatürk University. According to the correlation analysis results, it was determined that there was a positive correlation between the communication skills and the adaptation to teamwork. Accordingly, this explains the higher teamwork compatibility score average of the participants studying at Atatürk University.

Considering the communication skills and adaptation to teamwork according to sports branches of the participants, participants in team sports were found to have higher averages than the participants in the individual sports branches. When the related literature was reviewed, it was found that there was no study that investigates

the level of teamwork compatibility of the individuals who receive sports training.

In addition, there are studies showing that the athletes in team sports have a higher level of communication skills than those engaged in individual sports (Ulukan 2012).

When the participants' communication skills and adaptation to teamwork were investigated according to their departments, it was observed that the participants studying at the Physical Education and Sports Teaching Department had higher average scores than the students at the Sports Management and Coaching Education

Department. On the other hand, freshmen students were found to have higher averages of communication skills and teamwork compatibility according to their years in college. In the literature review on communication skills and teamwork compatibility according to department and years in college variables, it was found that there was no study on the adaptation to teamwork, whereas there were studies on communication skills with findings similar to this study (Tepeköylü et al 2009, Korkut 1997, Pehlivan 2005).

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Correspondence

Ali Gürbüz

E-mail: ali.gurbuz@msgsu.edu.tr